

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF COMPOSITE SANDWICH STRUCTURES WITH CORE OR FACE SHEET DISCONTINUITIES

E.R Fotsing, M. Sola, E. Ruiz^{*}, A. Ross

CREPEC, Chair on Composites of High Performance (CCHP), Department of Mechanical Engineering, École Polytechnique de Montréal, Montreal, Canada.

^{*} Corresponding author (edu.ruiz@polymtl.ca)

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1 Introduction

Composite sandwich structures offer good solutions to the aeronautic and automotive industries, where combining lightness, high stiffness and strength is essential. Composite sandwich structures consist of a thick lightweight core inserted between two thin composite sheets. The three layers are bonded together using an adhesive. The skins are usually made of metal or composite laminates and provide good in-plane and flexural stiffness. The core is metallic or non-metallic honeycomb or foam and provides good compressive and out of plane shearing properties.

Baseline composite sandwich structures are often modified for specific applications. In particular, various inserts are used either to improve properties or to assemble parts.

Because they are light and stiff, composite sandwiches are also good transmitters both for mechanical vibration and acoustic waves. Therefore, damping solutions are promoted in the industry to prevent mechanical damage or discomfort due to vibration and sound. One solution consists of inserting a constrained viscoelastic layer between face sheet plies [1, 2]. However, inserting viscoelastic layers can cause face sheet delamination [3, 4], weakening therefore the whole sandwich structure. The impact of delamination on the properties of the whole sandwich structure is not well documented and needs to be investigated.

Inserts are also implanted within the core either for vibration reduction or, more frequently, for assembly purposes [5]. As an example, inserts placed in the core are used for assembling and mounting airplane interior furniture made of composite sandwich panels. In addition, when manufacturing large parts made of many core pieces,

gaps can occur between pieces. In such cases, inserts or foam injections can be used in order to maintain the integrity of the core [6-8]. If the gaps are not filled, the real influence of these discontinuities on the core properties itself and on the mechanical properties of the whole sandwich structure must be assessed.

The purpose of this work is to study the influence of two types of discontinuities on the flexural properties of a composite sandwich structure. Interleaved viscoelastic layers between face sheet plies are evaluated through standard tensile testing of face sheets and three-point bending tests on sandwich beams. Gaps or breaks between core pieces are evaluated through three-point and four-point bending tests to provide shear modulus, ultimate strength and failure modes of the sandwich structure with core discontinuities. This work is carried out from a vibration viewpoint rather than fatigue or impact.

2 Experimental procedures

2.1 Panel sample manufacturing

Sandwich panels (400mmx400mmx14,3mm) were made of lightweight honeycomb core and woven carbon/epoxy fabric face sheets stacked in a [0/45]_s sequence. Panels were cured in an autoclave under controlled pressure and temperature following an aeronautic procedure. A 30 degree chamfer was cut on the edges of the honeycomb core to prevent crushing due to compaction pressure. The chamfer also allows a better pressure distribution and prevents fibre shifting during curing.

In order to assess the impact of core modifications, discontinuities were artificially created. **Figure 1** illustrates the creation of such discontinuities within the core. Small pieces of honeycomb were obtained by carefully debonding core sheets along the glue line in the ribbon direction (L direction). The pieces

were then joined together with no adhesive for sample 1 (called *cut modification*), or with a gap of 2 mm between two core pieces for samples 2 and 3 (called *gap modification*). Three panels with modified core and one reference panel were made in order to understand the importance of core discontinuities in a closed edge panel. The first panel contained 15 *cut modifications* (3 of which were placed in each shearing zone), the second panel had 2 *gap modifications* (one in each shearing zone) and the third panel had 15 *gap modifications* in the core (3 of which are placed in each shearing zone). It should be noted that “shearing zone” refers to zones of maximal shearing in three or four point bending tests. **Figure 2** illustrates the panels investigated with modified honeycomb core.

2.2 Beam samples with core modification

Another set of panels was manufactured using the same manufacturing procedure presented in section 2.1. From those panels, beams were cut using a diamond saw. Three reference beams and three beams with honeycomb discontinuity were cut to a 300x60mm² dimension. The discontinuities were placed transversely to the neutral axis of the beam. For beam samples, core modifications (*cut modification* or *gap modification*) were made in such a way that only one modification appears in the shearing zone.

2.3 Beam samples with viscoelastic inserts

In order to assess the influence of interleaved viscoelastic layers, sandwich beams (core not modified) having face sheets with viscoelastic inserts were manufactured. The viscoelastic material inserted in the face sheets was a Smacwrap ST film from Smac with a thickness of 0.2mm. Each beam was 250 mm long, 30 mm wide and had 2 inserts placed symmetrically under the outer layer of the top and bottom face sheet as seen on **Figure 3**. Each insert pair was placed at a different position along the longitudinal axis of the beams. In **Table 1**, the positions of the inserts are given in millimeters from one extremity of the beams. The size of each insert was 40x28mm².

Finally, beams made solely of face sheet laminates were produced. Each beam sample was 0.8 mm thick (1.0 mm with the insert), 30 mm wide and 254 mm long. Viscoelastic inserts of 40x20mm² and

40x28mm² were used, thus leaving 5mm and 1mm closed edges on each side of the insert, respectively. The viscoelastic layers were inserted under the top layer of carbon/epoxy composite face sheet before curing, as shown on **Figure 4**.

2.4 Testing procedure and parameters

In order to assess the influence of inserted viscoelastic films, tensile tests were performed on carbon/epoxy laminate beams according to ASTM standard D3039. Friction tabs made of the same material were bonded at both ends of the specimen to ensure good grip. The mechanical testing system had a 100kN load cell. Head speed was set to 2mm/min. An extensometer was used to record strain.

Three point bending test was performed on beams in order to evaluate the change of mechanical properties due to interleaved viscoelastic films between face sheet layers or to core discontinuities. The crosshead speed was set to 6mm/min. The loading bar has a diameter of 6.4 mm and the support bars have a diameter of 3.2 mm for a span of 230 mm. The test was stopped prior to failure. Position of the loading bar was recorded through a magnetic sensor with a precision of 1 micron. Panels were tested in four point bending configuration using the configuration shown on **Figure 5**. Three point bending and four point bending tests were done in accordance with ASTM C393 and D7250 standards.

The impact of skin modification was studied only for open edge beams whereas the influence of core discontinuities was investigated using composite sandwich beams and closed edge 400x400mm² chamfered panels.

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Influence of core discontinuity

Figure 6 shows the load-displacement curve for four point bending test of sandwich beams. It can be seen that the slope remains unchanged and are in agreement with the theory for beam samples regardless the nature of the core modification. Core discontinuities do not seem to impact the elastic behaviour of composite sandwich beams. However the load at failure decreases with increasing number of gap modifications in the sample. In fact the load

at failure varies from 1208 N for the reference sample to 1150 N for a sample with 3 *gap modifications*.

Figure 7 illustrates the load-displacement curve for closed edge panels with modified honeycomb core. It shows that the effect of core discontinuity becomes significant only with 15 *gap modifications* (i.e. 15 consecutive 2mm gaps). In fact a 12% decrease of the maximal load is observed for panel with 15 *gap modifications*, with a decrease of 14% in the modulus. Samples with *cut modifications* (i.e. pieces of honeycomb placed side-by-side without gap) and samples with small number of gaps have similar behavior as the reference panel (without discontinuities). This key conclusion suggests that core can be modified for different applications (assembly, damping treatment etc.) without altering the mechanical properties of the whole structure if the amount of discontinuities remains under a certain threshold. Regardless of the type of discontinuity, four point bending tests performed on closed edge panels led to failures oriented at 45° on the chamfer zone as shown on **Figure 8**. This failure mode is related to the stacking sequence the geometry of the panel and the loading configuration.

It should be pointed out that having 15 *gap modifications* within a 400x400mm² panel represents an extreme situation and does not reflect the reality. However the analysis made in this work contributes to a better understanding of the influence of such core discontinuities. Moreover, compression tests were not performed on beams or panel samples. This test would have revealed a completely different failure mode for the tested samples. Finally, impacts or fatigue (i.e. cyclic bending or tension / compression) were not investigated in this study.

3.2 Influence of skin modification

The Young's modulus for the standard skins (with no inserts) was calculated with the laminate theory using data from the manufacturer. It yields a value of 42.9 GPa, for a deviation of 3.5% with the experiments. These results validate both the manufacturing process and the quality of the parts (see **Table 2**). Tensile tests showed that the Young's modulus of the face sheet taken alone remained unchanged regardless of the width of the inserted viscoelastic layer (see **Figure 9**). The first 4000 µε

are shown on the graph. All three curves are identical and fairly linear.

The Young's modulus of the samples with inserts was calculated using ASTM D3039. The values in Table 2 are quite similar for all samples with respect to the reference, within the margin of error (i.e. deviation within 1%). Moreover the width of the insert, and thus the width of the closed borders do not change the tensile behaviour of the beam.

This result suggests that the mechanical properties of the laminate remain unaltered as long as the inserted viscoelastic layer is not thick enough to locally change the fiber orientation along the beam axis. Moreover, this result might also reflect the fact that curing thin viscoelastic films led to good adhesion at the carbon/epoxy/film interface avoiding any risks of delamination that can degrade the mechanical properties of the skin. These results are coherent with the assumption that there is no interlaminar stress in the part as long as the skin is in purely tensile state [1]. This assumption is considered in the next section, where skins with viscoelastic inserts are used in sandwich beams. Since the tensile properties of the skins are unchanged when viscoelastic materials are inserted, the change of the load-displacement slope of a three point bending test will be due to core shearing.

3.3 Bending of sandwich beams with face sheet discontinuity

Three point bending tests were conducted on sandwich beams having face sheets either with or without viscoelastic inserts. The results are presented on **Figure 10**. For the sake of clarity, only four load-displacement curves are displayed. The seven other curves are similar to the ones shown here. Two types of failures were observed: core shearing (e.g. insert at 175mm) and skin indentation (e.g. insert at 115mm). A typical test with core shearing is pictured on **Figure 11**, while **Figure 12** shows the case of skin indentation. Results obtained from Figure 10 with regards to the maximum load and failure mode are gathered in **Table 3**. The column "Side of rupture" in **Table 3** refers to the fact that failure occurs on one side or the other of the loading bar. The statement "With inserts" stands for core failure occurring in the half-beam containing the inserts; "No inserts" means that core failure occurred in the

half-beam with no inserts; and “Under the load” means that skin failure occurred at the loading bar contact point. **Figure 13** shows the maximum load for each insert with respect to its axial position in the skin. Squares are used to identify the center of the inserts on the horizontal axis, and the maximum loads on the vertical axis, whereas the lines represent insert span. The dashed line gives the position of the loading bar. It can be seen that all maximum loads are ranged between 619 N (i.e. the maximum load of the reference) and 540 N (i.e. the maximum load of the sample with inserts at 115 mm). The maximum load at rupture of samples which failed in skin indentation is significantly lower than the reference, and lower than all other samples. With respect to the reference beam, the maximal load is 10 % lower when the interleaved viscoelastic layer is under the loading bar (inserts located at 115 mm or 135 mm on **Table 3**). This decrease is less significant (less than 5 %) when the viscoelastic layer is placed elsewhere along the beam axis. Additionally, the Young’s modulus remains unchanged regardless of the position of the viscoelastic layers. This observation tends to confirm that interleaved viscoelastic layers do not change the tensile behavior of the sandwich face sheets.

All beams failed due to core shearing except when the viscoelastic layer was located directly under the loading bar. The core shearing failures in the samples is randomly distributed on either sides of the loading bar, suggesting that the viscoelastic layer is not the only weak spot of the sandwich structure. Samples with viscoelastic layers located directly under the loading bar underwent early indentation failure due to the compression of the bar. This is a common issue in honeycomb sandwich panels with localized loading. Therefore the influence of viscoelastic inserts in samples with no external load at the site of the inserts is more representative of the real life applications of such construction, except for impact situations.

4 Conclusions

It was shown that core discontinuities or face sheet modifications do not drastically affect the mechanical properties of the composite sandwich panel. In order to observe noticeable impact, the amount of open gaps in the core must be significant.

In the case of interleaved viscoelastic layers, behavior may be critical if the layer is located directly under the loading force, as could occur during impact. This investigation demonstrated that modifying core or face sheets of composite sandwich structure for assembly or vibration damping purposes can be done without altering the flexural mechanical properties of the sandwich.

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References

- [1] D.J. Mead “The measurement of the loss factors of beams and plates with constrained and unconstrained damping layer: a critical assessment” *J Sound Vib*, Vol. 300, pp. 744-762, 2007
- [2] E.R. Fotsing, M. Sola, A. Ross and E. Ruiz “Lightweight damping of composite sandwich beams; experimental analysis” *J Compos Mater*, DOI: 10.1177/0021998312449027
- [3] F. Xie, *et al.*, "Statistical Study of Delamination Area Distribution in Composite Components Fabricated by Autoclave Process," *Applied Composite Materials*, vol. 16, pp. 285-295, 2009.
- [4] A. Petras and M. P. F. Sutcliffe, "Failure mode maps for honeycomb sandwich panels" *Composite Structures*, vol. 44, pp. 237-252, 1999.
- [5] A. Strong, *Fundamentals of composites manufacturing: materials, methods and applications: Society of Manufacturing Engineers*, 2008.
- [6] B. J. Kim and D. G. Lee, "Characteristics of joining inserts for composite sandwich panels," *Composite Structures*, vol. 86, pp. 55-60, 2008.
- [7] E. Bozhevolnaya, *et al.*, "Local effects in the vicinity of inserts in sandwich panels," *Composites Part B: Engineering*, vol. 35, pp. 619-627.
- [8] E. Bozhevolnaya, *et al.*, "Local effects across core junctions in sandwich panels," *Composites Part B: Engineering*, vol. 34, pp. 509-517, 2003

Fig.1. Schematic of core modifications.

Fig.2. Schematic of core modifications in the panels.

Fig.3. Stacking sequence of the composites sandwich beam with interleaved viscoelastic layers.

Table 1 Position of inserts along the beam axis.

Sample	Position of the middle of the insert [mm]
0	15
2	35
4	55
6	75
8	95
10	115
12	135
14	155
16	175
18	195

Fig.4. Position of the viscoelastic film within the carbon/epoxy laminate.

Fig.5. Location of shearing zones in four-point bending tests.

Fig.6. Impact of modified core beams in four-point bending.

Fig.7. Impact of core discontinuities for close edge panels.

Fig.8. Chamfer failure.

Table 2 Tensile modulus of the skin laminates.

	Modulus [GPa]
Tensile sample 1	41,2
Tensile sample 2	41,8
Tensile sample 3	41,3
Average	41,4 ±0,4
Laminate theory	42,9
Deviation	3,49%

Fig.9. Modulus of skins with viscoelastic layers.

Fig.10. Three point bending test of sandwich beams with modified skins.

Fig.11. Typical three-point bending test after failure.

Fig.12. Core crush after skin indentation.

Table 3. Three-point bending test results of sandwich beams with modified skins.

Position of the insert [mm]	Maximum Load [N]	Deviation from reference	Side of rupture	Type of rupture	Displacement at failure [mm]
Reference	619	/	/	Shear	5,2
35	580	6,3%	With inserts	Shear	4,7
55	585	5,5%	No inserts	Shear	5,1
75	562	9,2%	With inserts	Shear	4,5
95	571	7,7%	No inserts	Shear	5,4
115	540	12,7%	Under the load	Skin	3,9
135	567	8,4%	Under the load	Skin	4,1
155	585	5,4%	With inserts	Shear	5,0
175	600	3,1%	No inserts	Shear	4,7
195	598	3,4%	With inserts	Shear	5,3
215	602	2,7%	With inserts	Shear	5,6

Fig.13. Load at failure in three-point bending test with respect to the position of inserts.